

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

D3.1 TOOLKIT OF SOIL HEALTH INDICATORS WITH METRICS

Toolkit of soil health indicators with metrics

Summary

The InBestSoil project, in its WP3, aims to give a monetary value to the ecosystem services (ES) provided by soils in different land uses. To achieve this, it is essential to quantitatively measure the different ES provided by a soil by selecting appropriate indicators. In this regard, a "Toolkit of Indicators" has been developed, including a selection of relevant and standardized indicators to assess the ES provided by the soil in various land uses. This toolkit is based on sets of indicators used in international and European statistics, as well as a review of scientific literature. Experts in soil health and ES indicators have been consulted to choose the most suitable indicators, tailored for each lighthouse and living labs included in the project.

The Toolkit includes indicators related to food and material provisioning, climate regulation, water and soil purification, nutrient cycling, biodiversity conservation, and cultural and recreational aspects. It is not designed to evaluate a single system, but rather to compare different systems and land uses, and highlight the effects of soil interventions. It can be used in full mode, calculating all available indicators, or in limited mode if data is missing for some indicators.

In the InBestSoil project, the indicators will be determined based on the data collected in different study areas (Lighthouses and Living Labs). These indicators will help assess the economic values of ES in different locations and based on different management practices. In summary, the Toolkit of Indicators provides a valuable tool for quantifying the ecosystem services provided by the soil and will assist in making informed decisions for the protection and improvement of soil health.

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1. Objectives

One of the goals of the WP3 of InBestSoil is to give a monetary value to the ecosystem services (ES) provided by soils under different land uses and biogeographic regions. Previously to perform a marketed or non-marketed valuation of the ES provided by soil, it is essential to quantitatively assess the value of the different ES in which soil is involved, by selection of suitable indicators. Thus, based on literature review, partners' own expertise and participatory research engaging experts on soil health indicators, we provide in this deliverable the final selection of indicators to assess the ES provided by soils with standardized metrics provided in the framework of a toolkit of indicators, tailored to the specific characteristics of each lighthouse and living lab of InBestSoil.

2. Introduction

Sixty to seventy per cent of European soils are severely or moderately degraded by compaction, contamination, erosion, and loss of organic matter (European Commission, 2021a). In fact, soil degradation costs more than 50 billion € per year only in the UE, and the global cost ranges from 5 to 8 trillion per year; thus, benefits of soil restoration exceed the costs by a factor of 6 (European Commission, 2021b). Nevertheless, activities that affect soil are not reported as such in companies' environmental reporting standards, or appear mixed in with other statistics (Davies, 2017). To address soil health issues, the business sector, policymakers, public administration and scientific community must join efforts to develop practices and policies that recognize and acknowledge the importance of soil for sustaining livelihoods, upholding biodiversity and regulating the earth's climate. Businesses must determine how their actions depend on the soil and exert an effect (positive or negative) on soil health.

In the mid-1940s, nature began to be introduced into economic activities to minimize the deterioration of ecosystems: the services provided by natural systems did not have an associated economic value and were therefore systematically ignored in financial transactions (Tao and Wallace, 2024). Giving value to these services made it possible to include them in the process of developing new economic policies. However, little attention has been paid to the economic services provided by soil (Anikwe and Ife, 2023). The quantitative assessment of soil health would make society aware of the multiple ecosystem services offered by soil and their economic value, and would facilitate the creation of business opportunities for protecting and improving soil health, with high net economic returns (Vanino et al., 2023).

Ecosystem services (ES) are benefits that humans obtain from ecosystems that support, directly or indirectly, their survival and quality of life (MEA, 2005). The Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, 2005) categorizes ecosystem services into four different classes:

- Provisioning services, the products obtained from ecosystems, including food, fibre, fuel, genetic resources, ornamental resources, freshwater, biochemical, natural medicines and pharmaceuticals.
- Regulating Services, the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes including air quality, climate, water, erosion, water purification and waste treatment, disease, pest, pollination and natural hazard.
- Supporting services, necessary for the production of all other ecosystem services. Some services, like erosion regulation, can be categorized as both a supporting and a regulating service. These services include soil formation, photosynthesis, primary production, and nutrient and water cycling.
- Cultural Services, the non-material benefits people obtain from ecosystems including cultural diversity, spiritual and religious values, knowledge systems, educational values, inspiration, aesthetic values, social relations, sense of place, cultural heritage values, recreation and ecotourism.

Thus, the first step to give an economic value to the ES associated with soil, is to define the most suitable indicators representing those ES, which will be quantified

to have a quantitative value of that ES in which soil contributes (Luján-Soto et al., 2020). The [Soil Mission Implementation Plan](#) has already identified eight different indicators to assess soil health: 1) Presence of pollutants, excess of nutrients and salts, 2) Soil organic carbon stock, 3) Soil structure, 4) Soil biodiversity, 5) Soil nutrients and acidity, 6) Vegetation cover, 7) Landscape heterogeneity, and 8) Forest cover. These indicators are quite general, and so there is a need to properly define the specific indicators. For instance, the indicator “soil biodiversity” can include any type of living organism in the soil and any type of index to quantify that diversity. Thus, it is important to decide what organism is going to be measured and the exact metrics for that. Our approach in InBestSoil project is to identify and select indicators that represent the delivery of ES by soil, most of which will be soil health indicators, but others will be also cultural. These indicators must be appropriate for different land uses such as agriculture, forestry, urban or industrial in different biogeographic regions included in InBestSoil project (Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, and Mediterranean).

3. Description of the case studies used in InBestSoil to assess soil health and quantify the economic market and non market value of the ecosystem services in which soil is involved

In order to understand the different soil health indicators co-selected under a participatory approach with experts, it is important to understand the characteristics of the different case studies implemented in InBestSoil project in which indicators will be used. Soil health indicators have been selected to match the specific characteristics and needs of each lighthouse and living lab included in the project (Luján-Soto et al., 2020), with different land uses (agricultural, forestry, urban and industrial) in four different biogeographic regions (Atlantic, Boreal, Continental, and Mediterranean).

InBestSoil is based on seven lighthouses (LH) and two living labs (LL) to develop the economic valuation of the ecosystem services associated to soil, and co-develop, co-design and decide business models based on healthy soils to foster public and private investments on soil health (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1. Map with the location of the lighthouses (LH) and living labs (LL) of InBestSoil, with the strategy followed in each of them.

Following the definitions given by the Implementation Plan for the Soil Mission, we consider a LH as a place for demonstration of long-term solutions, that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement. For the establishment of LLs, we use the definition proposed by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL). These LLs are intended as collaborations among some

research and innovation ecosystems, which involve regional stakeholders in systemic research and codesign, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health. The LHs are selected as representatives of the implementation of sustainable management practices that have led to high soil health under important land uses in the EU. They will act as innovation and demonstration ecosystems to accelerate the co-creation and uptake of solutions to enhance soil health in the EU, by the development of a proper ecosystem for investment and generation of business models.

Thus, each LH is based on an area with the long-term implementation of sustainable interventions to enhance soil health. In addition, each LH has also identified a nearby area with unsustainable management practices associated to low soil health, used as reference or baseline to compare soil health between two contrasting scenarios (long-term sustainable management vs unsustainable management leading to high soil health vs low soil health, respectively). As a result, these LHs are examples for demonstration solutions and engagement of practitioners and key stakeholders to accelerate the innovation uptake. Each of the two LLs include between 10 and 20 farms (agricultural land use in the Mediterranean and Continental biogeographic regions) that operate at a subregional level, in which experiments involving land managers, farmers, farmers' organizations, businesses, scientific community, policymakers, and industries, among others, are coordinated, to test, monitor and evaluate practical solutions to develop business with interventions that enhance soil health.

The rationale for the selection of the LHs and LLs to be used as innovation ecosystems is as follows: i) they are the most dominant land uses in Europe with 84.6% of the total European surface (Eurostat, 2018), ii) they are included in the most extensive biogeographic regions of Europe, covering 87.1% of the total surface (European Commission, 2010), iii) they are a good demonstration of sustainable vs unsustainable practices to enhance soil health, which have been co-designed between wide range of actors in the value chain, and iv) they already have a community of stakeholders collaborating to make business and increase economic revenues by enhancing soil health.

To properly understand the characteristics, needs and challenges of InBestSoil LHs and LLs, we provide in Annex 1 a detailed description of each of them.

4. How to evaluate soil health and their involvement in ecosystem services: the toolkit of indicators

To make the concept of ES operational with respect to sustainability evaluation in different land uses, the ES must be quantified to detect changes as a function of changing conditions (Rigo et al., 2024). However, measuring the ES is not always practically attainable, given the nature of some of them and the limitations in the number of measures that can be realistically carried out in the field. Metrics and indicators are essential to assess and communicate the current status and interactions of ES and their contribution towards land use sustainability (Canedoli et al., 2024). They allow understanding if the trend of ES is favourable or not and if proposed alternative managements are increasing or decreasing the overall sustainability (Dale et al., 2024). This will help design management practices and policies that ensure the sustainable flow of ES to support human welfare and maintain biodiversity (Rigo et al., 2024).

Indicators are useful for informing about the status of a system, for interpreting and summarizing complex processes, and for communicating effectively with stakeholders (Peng et al., 2023). In general, the term 'indicator' refers to quantifiable and measurable attributes of a system and might supply information on other variables or processes that are difficult to access or to describe. Indicators should respond to the following characteristics (Layke et al., 2012):

- i. Intuitive. Indicators point out information about ES clearly without ambiguity. It is of particular importance that indicators are easily understood by policymakers and other non-technical end-users.
- ii. Sensitive. Indicators are able to detect changes timely in order to give early warnings of undesirable changes.
- iii. Accepted. They are scientifically-based and transparent in terms of calculation methodology, data availability and evaluation

Since a single indicator cannot meet all the requirements, a set of indicators (toolkit) is needed to describe key attributes of ecological systems of interest (Dale et al., 2004). A first analysis of the studies conducted so far on the selection and application of indicators to assess the sustainability of different land uses has shown that there has been an important effort to design a comprehensive or targeted set of indicators (Rutigliano et al., 2023; Froger et al., 2024; Gutiérrez et al., 2024; Seré et al., 2024).

The toolkit of indicators proposed in InBestSoil was defined based on the sets already used for international and European statics and surveys (i.e., OECD, FAO, Eurostat, etc.) and by a literature review on scientific publications. We have also exploited the results of previous and ongoing EU projects (i.e., H2020 projects Fatima, Diverfarming, DiverIMPACTS, SoildiverAgro). Although each land use may prioritize soil indicators depending on their problems/challenges/needs, several ES that are supported by soils have been already identified from those presented in MAES (van der Meulen and Maring, 2018) and CICES (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018), as well as the main soil indicators that represent those ES based on literature and project outputs.

Thus, based on this literature review, project outputs and own expertise of partners, the **ES proposed in InBestSoil to be selected and prioritized** in each of the LHs/LLs based on their specific characteristics are the following:

- a. Provisioning ecosystem services
 - Provision of food (Cultivated crops that can be harvested for direct use and used as raw material for the production of food)
 - Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials (Biomass or inorganic materials for direct use and/or processed as fibre, energy or for construction)
 - Provision of water (Surface water retained by soil)
- b. Regulating ecosystem services
 - Climate regulation (Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere (global regulation) and the air temperature and humidity (micro and regional regulation))
 - Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction (Bio-remediation and filtration / sequestration / storage / accumulation of water, wastes or toxic substances)
 - Nutrient cycling (Originating, storing, transforming, recycling and transferring nutrients from soils into plants)
 - Flood regulation and water storage (Regulation of water flow that mitigates or prevents potential damage to economic assets and human lives)
 - Erosion control (Control of erosion rates, including buffering and attenuation of mass movement)
- c. Supporting ecosystem services
 - Biodiversity (variety of organisms living in the soil)
 - Habitat for organisms (Landscape heterogeneity for maintaining nursery populations and habitats, including gene pool protection)
- d. Cultural ecosystem services
 - Cultural heritage (Characteristics or features (tangible) of soil systems that have a bequest value to the conservation of physical artefacts of human cultural heritage (such as structures, objects and organisms))
 - Cultural identity (Characteristics or features (non-tangible) of soil systems that have symbolic meaning and contributes to the promotion of spiritual sense of belonging, traditional knowledge, and associated customs in social systems where they are embedded)
 - Recreation (Characteristics of soil systems that enable its physical use by activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions)
 - Aesthetics (Characteristics of soil systems that enable aesthetic experiences or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions)
 - Information for cognitive development (Contribution of soil systems to the acquisition of knowledge)

Thus, the **procedure** followed to select the soil health indicators for each LL and LH based on key ES that those soil deliver is the following:

- i. A **preliminary list of indicators representing the different ES related to healthy soils** was established by project partners based on their own expertise, literature review and outputs of other projects (Annex 2).

- ii. Based on this complete list of soil health indicators related to specific ES, **consultations with experts** in soil health indicators and the delivery of ES by healthy soils were performed. For this purpose, a **web-based survey system** was used to query about the importance (values) experts place across a range of ES and indicators. Experts were selected for each LL/LH, by LH/LL leaders, in order to have a representation of the following **target groups**:
 - a. Users (Direct users and technicians who work directly in the ecosystem of each LH/LL, such as farmers and agricultural technicians, foresters...),
 - b. Researchers (Scientists, engineers and/or environmentalists who conducted research in the ecosystems of each LH/LL),
 - c. Public managers (Managers from local, regional and national organisations responsible for soil and land use management in each LH/LL), and
 - d. Civil society (NGOs, trade unions, political parties, and other civil associations representing social interest for the region where LH/LL are embedded).
- iii. Based on the list provided in Annex 2, experts had to **select and prioritize the ES** that are important for their specific LH/LL. Once the ES were selected, next step was to **select the most suitable soil health indicators for those ES** selected. Finally, experts had to prioritize the soil health indicators selected.

Thus, the Toolkit of indicators we propose for InBestSoil is the result of the outputs of the consultation with experts and project partners own expertise, tailored to the specific characteristics, needs and challenges of each LH and LL.

5. Toolkit of indicators

In this section we provide the ES selected for each LH and LL, and the soil health indicators selected to represent them. Thus, the ES and soil health indicators to be measured in each LH and LL are different, identified and selected based on their specific characteristics, needs and challenges.

5.1. LH1. Mediterranean Forestry Soil: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Plant biomass	kg/ha
	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	mg/kg
	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Soil sealing	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Richnes of Microarthropods richness, abundance and biomass and soil biological quality based on arthropods (QBSar index)	Species number, number/m ² , g/m ² and dimensionless (1-20)
	Spider richness and abundance	species number and number/day
	Copropagous fauna richness, abundance and acivity	species number, number/day and % of mass loss
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Type of forest species	number
	Plant richness, biodiversity and density	Number, dimensionless and plants/m ²
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.2. LH2. Mediterranean Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by metallic mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Plant biomass	kg/ha
	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	mg/kg

Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Soil sealing	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Type of forest species	number
	Plant richness, biodiversity and density	Number, dimensionless and plants/m ²
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.3. LH3. Atlantic Industrial Soil: Restoration of contaminated soil by copper mining activities using artificial soils (Technosols).

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Plant biomass	kg/ha
	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	mg/kg

Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Soil sealing	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Type of forest species	number
	Plant richness, biodiversity and density	Number, dimensionless and plants/m ²
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.4. LH4. Continental Urban Soil: Carbon sequestration and flood mitigation capacity of agricultural and forest uses in urban soils.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	
	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless

Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ or $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}$
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements	%
	Rotation length and sequence	yr and number
	Intercropping species	number
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.5. LH5. Boreal Urban Soil: Impact of urban agriculture on soil heath.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	
	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless

Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements	%
	Rotation length and sequence	yr and number
	Intercropping species	number
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.6. LH6. Boreal Forestry Soil: Effects planting strategies, fertilization, and sustainable soil management on soil health.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Wood production	kg/ha
	Vegetation cover	%
	Forest cover (density of trees)	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha

Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	mg/kg
	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm^3 and cm^3/cm^3
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Soil sealing	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	$\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ or $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kg}$
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Type of forest species	number
	Plant richness, biodiversity and density	Number, dimensionless and plants/m ²
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)

Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.7. LH7. Atlantic Agricultural Soil: Sustainable practices (crop diversification, minimum tillage, fertilization reduction...) around the inclusion of a new crop in the area: lupines.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
	Exchangeable Na, electrical conductivity and pH	mg/kg, dS/m
Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless

Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements	%
	Rotation length and sequence	yr and number
	Intercropping species	number
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.8. LL1. Mediterranean Agricultural Soil : Application of conservation agriculture practices, as potential climate change adaptation and mitigation strategies: effects on soil health and crop production.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
	Exchangeable Na, electrical conductivity and pH	mg/kg, dS/m

Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements	%
	Rotation length and sequence	yr and number
	Intercropping species	number
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

5.9. LL2. Continental Agricultural Soil: Adoption of sustainable management to enhance C sequestration and soil health.

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Provisioning		
Provision of food	Crop yield	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Dimensionless
Provision of water	Water content at field capacity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Regulating		
Climate regulation	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Dimensionless
	Net Primary Productivity (NPP) and Gross Primary Productivity (GPP)	g/m ² /yr
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	t/ha
	Nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	ng/g
	Exchangeable Na, electrical conductivity and pH	mg/kg, dS/m

Nutrient cycling	Total and mineral nitrogen	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	cmol/kg and %
Flood regulation and water storage	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Soil depth	cm
	Particle size and coarse fragments	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Dimensionless
Erosion control	Vegetation cover	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	km
	Bare soil index	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Supporting		
Biodiversity	Total microbial biomass	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Presence of natural green elements	%
	Rotation length and sequence	yr and number
	Intercropping species	number
	Soil sealing	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Unit
Cultural		
Cultural heritage	Presence of cultural elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of ancestral vestiges	Yes/No (binary)
Cultural identity	Presence of traditional elements	Yes/No (binary)
	Presence of origin certification labeling	Yes/No (binary)
Recreation	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	0–1 Index (continuous)
	Recreation Index	1-17 Index (discrete)
	Visitors and accomodations	Number/ha
Aesthetics	Aesthetic landscape Index	1-11 Index (discrete)
	Photo elicitation intensitiy index	Number photos/ha (continuous)
Information for cognitive development	Employment generation	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number (continuous)

6. How to use the Toolkit of indicators

Indicators are useful tools for science, policy-making, decision-making, advisors and businesses to assess the environmental, economic and societal impact of interventions on different land uses (Froger et al., 2024; Gutiérrez et al., 2024). The main characteristic of indicators is their ability to summarise, focus and condense the complex information arising from research into understandable and manageable concepts (Luján-Soto et al., 2020). The Toolkit of indicators proposed in InBestSoil includes, in a coherent framework, the most relevant indicators particularly suitable for a comprehensive assessment of the ES provided by soil in different land uses and biogeographic regions.

The toolkit is not suitable for evaluating a single system. In fact, for the indicators that are included in it, neither maximum nor minimum values or thresholds have been indicated, unless these are required by mandatory regulations. Instead, the indicators must be used for the comparison of different systems, land uses or management, in order to highlight the effects of the interventions. Hence, a single value of an indicator provides meaningless information if it is decontextualized with respect to comparable situations. The toolkit, according to data availability, can be used in a full mode, i.e., by calculating all the indicators, or in a limited mode, if data for calculation are not present, and data should be conveniently displayed as differences among the two or more systems in comparison. A nice way to display the results is through web graphs.

As for the specific use of the toolkit in InBestSoil, the indicators will be calculated using the soil collected in WP3 and analysed in the laboratory, and vegetation, crop, social, economic and cultural data also collected in the different lighthouses and living labs. The indicators will be used to further assess the economic market and non-market values of the different ES in all lighthouses and living labs, in terms of the different managements and interventions.

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Annex 1 – Description of the lighthouses and living labs used in InBestSoil

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures

PEDOClimatic REGION: MEDITERRANEAN
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL
COUNTRY: SPAIN
LOCATION: TALAVÁN (EXTREMADURA)
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 16,7 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 644 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): CAMBISOLS,
LUVISOLS, ACRISOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Restoration of soil by rotational grazing managing in woody pastures

- LEARNING AND DEMONSTRATION FARM
- COLLABORATIVE SPACE
- TESTED REGENERATIVE GRAZING
- ORGANIC PRODUCTION
- MONITORING OF PASTURES AND BIODIVERSITY
- 232 HA OF PASTURE
- AUTOCHTHONOUS BREEDS OF CATTLE AND SHEEP
- IMPROVED PRODUCTION AND MARKETING

LIGHTHOUSE #1: Soil health threats

- Low below and aboveground biodiversity
- Erosion
- Overgrazing
- Low soil quality
- Low soil organic matter content
- Landscape simplification

LIGHTHOUSE #1: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 5,94 ha,
- Geographical coordinates: 39.71294, -6.25808
- Year of establishment: 2019
- Current vegetation type / cropping system (to choose between both): Dehesa
- Main vegetation species / crops (to choose between both): leguminous plants and Gramineae, and trees typically of the *Quercus* genus (holm oaks) which are in good condition, together with a high presence of a shrub layer composed mainly of rockroses, genista, broom and lavender.
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Rotational grazing
 - Non sowing and tillage
 - High intensity grazing + Short time of grazing + Enough resting time
 - Autochthonous breeds: Blanca cacereña
- Main economic activities: cow meat production
- Actors involved: CICYTEX, Fundación Entretantos

LIGHTHOUSE #3: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 18,1 ha
- Geographical coordinates: 39.71634, -6.26137
- Year of establishment of current management: 1993
- Current vegetation type / cropping system (to choose between both): Dehesa
- Main vegetation species / crops (to choose between both): leguminous plants and Gramineae, and trees typically of the *Quercus* genus (holm oaks) which are in good condition, together with a high presence of a shrub layer composed mainly of rockroses, genista, broom and lavender.
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health:
 - Reforestation
 - Continuous tillage over years
 - Lack of livestock
- Main economic activities: cow meat production

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #2: Restoration of contaminated soil – Cartagena, Spain

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: MEDITERRANEAN

LAND USE: INDUSTRIAL – FORMER METALLIC MINE

COUNTRY: SPAIN

LOCATION: CARTAGENA

GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATES: 37.594005, -0.886302

MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 17 °C

MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 280 MM

SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): TECHNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #2: Soil health threats

- Soil and water pollution
- Hyperacidification
- Hypersulfation
- Low/null nutrients and organic matter contents
- Metallic (Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn) contamination
- Non-metallic (As) contamination
- Secondary Salinization
- Null vegetation cover

LIGHTHOUSE #2: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

Santa Antonieta Mine (remediated in 2012)

- **Extension/Location:** 1 ha/coordinates: 37.5994005,-0.886302
- Year of establishment: 2012
- **Current vegetation type:** Mediterranean shrubland
- **Main vegetation species:** *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia Rosmarinus*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, *Hyparrhenia hirta*
- The **remediation project consisted of** the creation of artificial soils (Technosols) applying the aided phytostabilization technique based on the combination of heavy metal-tolerant plants (phytostabilisation) and organic or inorganic amendments (chemical stabilisation), aims to reduce soil metal bioavailability while improving soil health.
- **Main economic activities:** tourism as guided tours to mines.
- **Actors involved:**
 - Portman Golf SL. Owner of the land (private)
 - Regional Government of Murcia (public)
 - ANSE. Ecologist NGO
 - Fundación Sierra Minera. Private foundation for the protection of the former mining district
 - Regional and local governments

LIGHTHOUSE #2: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

Santa Antonieta Mine

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

San Francisco Javier Mine (non remediated)

- Extension/ Location: 5 ha / coordinates: 37.593997, -0.881523
- Year of establishment of current management: tailings abandoned since 1950's up to 1970's
- Current vegetation type: none
- Main vegetation species: none
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health: metallic mining (mostly Pb, Zn and Fe)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #3: Restoration of contaminated soil – Touro, Spain

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: ATLANTIC
LAND USE: INDUSTRIAL – COPPER MINING
COUNTRY: SPAIN
LOCATION: TOURO (GALICIA)
GEOGRAPHICAL COORDINATES: 42.879, -8.321
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 12.7 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 1242 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): TECHNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #3: Soil health threats

- Soil and water pollution
 - Hyperacidification
 - Hyperoxidation with Fe⁺³
 - Hypersulfation
 - Heneraluminization
 - Metallic contamination (Mn, Cu, Zn, Ni)
- Extremophile Ecosystems
- Bio-catalysis acceleration caused by oxygen-reduction reaction.

LIGHTHOUSE #3: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension/ Location: 30 ha, coordinates: 42.878, -8.321
- Year of establishment: 1999
- Current vegetation type: Atlantic
- Main vegetation species: Autochthonous herbaceous and shrubby plants
- The remediation project consisted in the production of artificial soils (Technosols), specifically designed to counter-act the hazardous properties of soil contamination caused by mining activities.
 - Technosol #1: Eutrophic Andic Soil
 - Technosol #2: sambaqui
- Main economic activities: Production of aggregates for construction
- Actors involved:
 - CVAN – Centro de Valorización Ambiental del Norte
 - Francisco Gómez Cia (Land Owner)
 - Explotaciones Gallegas (Previous land owner)
 - TEN – Tratamientos Ecológicos del Noroeste

LIGHTHOUSE #3: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- Extension/ Location: 15 ha, coordinates 42.877, -8.319
- Year of establishment of current management: 1999
- Current vegetation type: No vegetation
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health:
 - Copper Mining
 - Aggregates production
- Main economic activities: Production of aggregates for construction

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #4: Urban soils

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: TEMPERATE CONTINENTAL
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL, FOREST
COUNTRY: CROATIA
LOCATION: ZAGREB
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 6,2 – 11,4 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 859,4 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): STAGNOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #4: Soil health threats

- Overexploitation
- Low biodiversity
- Structural deterioration
- Low soil quality
- Soil compaction
- Low soil organic matter content
- Soil abandonment
- Flood risk

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (1)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 2007.
- **Current vegetation type:** apple orchard
- **Main vegetation species:** apple orchard
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Mulching
 - Low soil disturbance
 - Permanent grass cover
 - Appropriate fertilisation
- **Main economic activities:** apple production
- **Actors involved:** The area is under the supervision of the Faculty of Agriculture

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (2)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 1996.
- **Current vegetation type:** Grassland
- **Main vegetation species:** grass-clover mixtures
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Mulching
 - No soil disturbance
 - Permanent vegetation cover
- **Main economic activities:** no economic value
- **Actors involved:** The area is under the supervision of the Faculty of Agriculture

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (3)

- **Extension:** 50 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.18
- **Year of establishment:** >200 years
- **Current vegetation type:** Forest
- **Main vegetation species:** *Quercus petraea* - *Robinia pseudoacacia*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - No soil disturbance
 - No mineral fertilization
 - Natural decay of trees and leaves
- **Main economic activities:** wood stock
- **Actors involved:** area is under supervision of Faculty of Forestry

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (4)

- **Extension:** 1 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.17
- **Year of establishment:** 1991.
- **Current vegetation type:** secondary forest (afforested)- abandoned agricultural land
- **Main vegetation species:** Shrubbery
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - No soil disturbance
- **Main economic activities:** no economic value
- **Actors involved:** not permitted

LIGHTHOUSE #4: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- **Extension:** 20 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** N 45.85, E 16.18
- **Year of establishment of current management:** 2007.
- **Current vegetation type / cropping system:** annual cropland
- **Main vegetation species / crops:** winter wheat, winter barley, winter oats, soybean, maize
- **Management practices performed that led to low soil health:**
 - Conventional tillage
 - Intensive mineral fertilization
 - Lack of organic fertilization
 - Absence of cover cropping
 - Absence of mulching

- **Main economic activities:** certified seed production (wheat, soybean)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

LIGHTHOUSE #5: Impact of urban agriculture on soil health

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: BOREAL
LAND USE: AGRICULTURAL, GRASSLAND,
COUNTRY: LITHUANIA
LOCATION: VILNIUS
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 7.2 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 764 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): *ANTROPOSOLS*

LIGHTHOUSE #5: Soil health threats

- Flood risk
- Soil erosion
- Soil compaction
- Soil pollution
- Reduced biodiversity
- Reduced organic matter

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban Garden)

- **Extension:** 0.17 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7253296 N; 25.2785659 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1960
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban garden
- **Main vegetation species:** cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkins and strawberries
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Composting;
 - Mulching;
 - No tillage
 - No agrochemicals use
- **Main economic activities:** vegetable production
- **Actors involved:** Small scale farmers

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban garden)

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban park)

- **Extension:** 1.19 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7268095 N; 25.2760011 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1995
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban forest
- **Main vegetation species:** *Quercus robur* (L.)
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Reduced grass management
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Vilnius Municipality

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH (Urban park)

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban grassland)

- **Extension:** 0.09 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7250879 N; 25.2783507 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1960
- **Current vegetation type:** Urban grassland
- **Main vegetation species:** *Leotodum taraxacoides*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Reduced grass management
 - Composting
 - No agrochemicals use
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Small scale farmers

LIGHTHOUSE #5: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH (Urban grassland)

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH (Lawn)

- **Extension:** 0.96 ha
- **Geographical coordinates:** 54.7270868 N; 25.2792543 E
- **Year of establishment:** 1995
- **Current vegetation type:** Lawn
- **Main vegetation species:** *Leotodum taraxacoides*
- **Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:**
 - Intensive grass management
- **Main economic activities:** None
- **Actors involved:** Vilnius Municipality

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH (Lawn)

LIGHTHOUSE #6: Boreal forestry Soil

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: BOREAL

LAND USE: FOREST (FOREST WITH TERRAIN, RECULTIVATED MINE, WITH WOOD ASH FERTILIZED FOREST)

COUNTRY: LATVIA

LOCATION: FOREST LANDSCAPE (REGION)

MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: +5.9 °C

MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 700 MM

LIGHTHOUSE #6: Soil health threats

- Low below and aboveground biodiversity
- Erosion – GHG emissions
- Low soil quality – risk of insufficient nutrient availability
- Low soil organic matter content
- Landscape simplification
- Acidity of organic and mineral soils
- Inappropriate groundwater level

LIGHTHOUSE #6: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 9917 ha,
- Geographical coordinates: 57.330699, 25.950759
- Year of establishment: 1960 regional nature protection territory. As research territory since 1999. Since 2001 State forest research area.
- Current vegetation type - forest
- Pine, spruce, birch and other forest vegetation (EU habitats 6450, 7160, 91E0, 9080)
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health:
 - Balance of nutrient elements
 - Afforestation/ reforestation –promotion of forest vegetation formation
 - Tending /thinning - increase of soil radiation for species in vegetation cover
 - 'Gentle' soil preparation
- Main economic activities: Forestry, nature protection, education, science
- Actors involved: Forest research station, Ministry of Agriculture, University of life sciences and technologies.

NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 10 ha and 6ha
- Geographical coordinates: 57.330699, 25.950759
- Year of establishment of current management:
- Current ; former sand and gravel mining site/ furrows cause soil erosion
- Main vegetation species / crops (to choose between both): Bushes willows, forest tree species
- Management practices performed that led to low soil health:
 - Mining area set aside no following activities or recultivation due to change of ownership.
 - Steep terrain – forest machines could no move perpendicular - soil erosion in furrows
 - Bare soil –leading to lack of nutrient elements in semi mature too dense planted forests
 - Ultra-wet growing conditions
- Main economic activities: No current activities in mining site, tending in regenerated forest area. Monitoring of experimental sites to fix low soil health parameters and dynamic.

Other NEARBY CONTROL AREA WITH LOW SOIL HEALTH

Lighthouse #7: Regenerative crop management for Soil Health

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: ATLANTIC
LAND USE: AGRICULTURE
COUNTRY: NETHERLANDS
REGION: BETUWE
MEAN ANNUAL TEMPERATURE: 10.6 °C
MEAN ANNUAL PRECIPITATION: 848 MM
SOIL TYPE (WORLD REFERENCE BASE): ANTROPOSOLS

LIGHTHOUSE #7: Soil threats

- Water management
- Compaction
- Soil and water pollution

LIGHTHOUSE #7: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

- Extension: 130 ha
- Year of establishment: 2005
- Soil type (World Reference Base): Fluvisol
- Mean annual temperature and precipitation: 10,6°C and 848 mm
- Location: 51.94129253, 5.69297944
- Current cropping system: biodynamic, regenerative
- Main crops: Onion, pumpkin, potato, grass-clover, lupin, peas, sugarmaize, wheat, rye
- Sustainable management practices performed that permitted high soil health and economic development:
 - Wide crop rotation
 - Organic farming
 - Reduced tillage
 - N-fixers
 - Green manures
- Main economic activities: Crop sales, projects, education, specialized hired labour
- Actors involved: WUR, Lekker Lupine, Agrifirm, Baltussen

LIGHTHOUSE #7: REPRESENTATIVE OF HIGH SOIL HEALTH

NEARBY CONTROL AREA: DIJKEHOEVE

- Extension: 5 ha
- Year of establishment: 2010?
- Location Soil type (World Reference Base): Fluvisol
- Mean annual temperature and precipitation: 10.8 C and 832mm
- Location: 51.839667, 5.982910
- Current cropping system:
- Main crops: Green manure (now), Barley, Potatoes, Winter wheat, onions, broad beans, sugar beets
- Current management practices :
 - Conventional farming
 - Chemical pest control
 - Tillage
 - Cover crops
 - Wide crop rotation
- Main economic activities:
 - Crop production

NEARBY CONTROL AREA: DIJKEHOEVE

- Currently under green manure (now) consisting mostly of a mix of grains and brassica
- Previous crops (from more recent to less recent): Barley, Potatoes, Winter wheat, onions, broad beans, sugar beets

Living lab #1: Alternative management to face climate change

PEDOCLIMATIC REGION: Mediterranean
LAND USE: Agriculture
COUNTRY: Italy
REGION: **Sardinia**
NUMBER OF LIGHTHOUSES (LH) INCLUDED: 2
NUMBER OF LIVING LAB EXPERIMENTAL SITES (LLES) INCLUDED: 9
TOTAL CURRENT NUMBER OF MEMBERS: ~20

LIVING LAB #1: Soil threats

- Environmental conditions: worsened by climate change and polluted soils.
- Land abandonment due to low profitability of agricultural activities.
- Soil fertility reduction (common to other Mediterranean areas).
- Water scarcity & extreme events: Reduced sustainability of rainfed extensive crops such as cereals, forages etc. and animal husbandry such as breeding sheep in hilly areas etc.

VINEYARD erosion in hilly areas

**Soil Erosion with extreme heavy rains
FLOODING IN PLAINS**

LIVING LAB #1: Possible solutions to enhance soil health and promote economic activity

Conservation agriculture:

- Minimizing or avoiding soil disturbance through reduced tillage (RT) and sod seeding (SS o NT).
- Maintaining permanent soil cover through residue management and cover crops.
- Promoting plant diversity through crop rotation.

Tillage reduction

Rotation with legumes

REDUCED EROSION	MITIGATES GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS
IMPROVED SOIL STRUCTURE, ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT, AND FERTILITY	STABILIZES YIELDS
CONSERVATION OF SOIL WATER CONTENT	HELPS MAINTAINING CULTIVATION IN DISADVANTAGED RURAL AREAS
REDUCES CULTIVATION COSTS	ENHANCED SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES

Cover cropping

Living Lab #1: Sardinian LTE on Conservation Agriculture

The **lighthouse** of the **LL1** is composed by two experimental sites: Ussana and Benatzu, Italy

The two sites are only 1 km away from each other with great differences in soil fertility.

Experimental Design: split-plot design with 3 complete randomized blocks

Tillage treatments (main plots - 2400 m²)

- no tillage or **Sod Seeding (SS)**
- minimum or **Reduced Tillage (RT)**
- **Conventional Tillage (CT)**

Crop rotations (sub-plots - 600 m²)

- single cropping with durum wheat (CW - Continuous Wheat)
- durum wheat/legume crop rotation (LW - Legumes/Wheat)

From 2015 changes in rotation treatments due to phytopathology problems caused by accumulation of nematodes (Foxi et al, 2017) especially with Continuous Wheat and Conventional Tillage.

Therefore CW was replaced by two new rotations treatments:

- wheat/faba bean rotation (**FW** – faba bean/wheat)
- wheat/field pea rotation (**PW** – field pea/wheat)

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #SS1:

- Extension: **3.84 ha**
- Year of establishment: **2009**
- Location: 39.5415 N, 8.9008 E
- Current cropping system: sod seeding and durum wheat/legume (*Trifolium*)
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - Rotation cereals - legumes.
 - Since 2009 sod seeding and rotation between cereals and legumes
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #RT2:

- Extension: 2.93 ha
- Year of establishment: 2023
- Location: 39.5670 N, 8.8542 E
- Previous cropping system: reduced tillage/ripper (conventional) and durum wheat/legume (*Trifolium spp*)
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - Rotation cereals - legumes.
 - From 2023 reduced tillage.
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #CT3:

- Extension: **1.7 ha**
- Year of establishment: 2023
- Location: 39.5648 N, 8.8517 E
- previous cropping system: reduced tillage/ripper (conventional) and durum wheat/legume (*Trifolium* spp.)
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - Rotation cereals - legumes.
 - From 2023 sod seeding.
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #SS4:

- Extension: **7.8 ha**
- Year of establishment: **2010**
- Location: 39.4661 N, 9.0349 E
- Current cropping system: sod seeding and durum wheat/legume (Fava bean) rotation
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - Rotation cereals - legumes.
 - Since 2010 sod seeding and rotation between cereals and legumes
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #RT5:

- Extension: **1 ha**
- Year of establishment: **2023**
- Location: 39.4653 N, 9.0280 E
- Current cropping system: reduced tillage/ripper (conventional) and durum wheat/legume (Fava bean) rotation
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - rotation cereals - legumes.
 - From 2023 reduced tillage.
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #CT6:

- Extension: **3.3 ha**
- Year of establishment: **2023**
- Location: 39.4802 N, 9.0561 E
- Previous cropping system: reduced tillage/ripper (conventional) and durum wheat/legume (Fava bean) rotation
- Main crops: durum wheat
- Current management practices:
 - rotation cereals - legumes.
 - From 2023 sod seeding.
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #SS7:

- Extension: 10 ha
- Year of establishment: 2007
- Location: 39.6348 N, 8.6374 E
- Current cropping system: sod seeding (wheat/maize)
- Main crops: durum/soft wheat
- Current management practices:
 - Rotation durum/soft wheat.
 - Since 2010 sod seeding and rotation between cereals and legumes.
 - From 2017 wheat/maize rotation.
- Main economic activities: Production of durum wheat for bread and pasta and legumes for feed/food.

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #ORG8:

- Extension: **1.2 ha**
- Year of establishment: **2017**
- Location: 39.1207 N, 8.9933 E (Cantine Nuraghe Antigori - <https://www.cantinenuragheantigori.it/>)
- Previous cropping system: organic farming, reduced tillage
- Main crops: vineyard (Carignano)
- Current management practices:
 - Organic farming
 - Since 2023 cover crops
- Main economic activities: Production of organic wine

EXPERIMENTAL SITE #RT9:

- Extension: 1 ha
- Year of establishment: Centuries-old olive trees from around the 1940s; owned since 2017
- Mean annual temperature and precipitation: Minimum 11.1 °C, average maximum 22.2 °C. and 560 mm
- Location: 40.7846 N, 8.5550 E
- Current cropping system: Organic
- Main crops: Olive groves
- Current management practices:
 - Before 2017: Left uncultivated/grazed, no tillage.
 - After 2017: Tillage with discs in April or May, depending on the application of organic fertilization. Organic fertilization was carried out in April, and an early ploughing was performed immediately after fertilisation. In years when organic fertilization was not applied, it has been worked with discs in May as a measure to remove the grass cover. Pruning in 2019, and the pruning residues were burned. Soil fertilization with 350 kg/hectare of organic fertilizers in 2021 and 2023.
 - Since 2024 onwards: no-tillage practices; control of the grass cover will be managed through shredding, and pruning residues will be shredded..
- Main economic activities: Production of oil and olives; sale of large-sized pruning wood

LL #2: Continental agricultural soil

Pedoclimatic Region: **Continental**

Land Use: **Agriculture**

Country: **Switzerland**

REGION: **Baselland**

Number Of **Lighthouses (LH)** included: **3 (OUT OF 10)**

Number of **Living Lab Experimental Sites (LLES)** included: **1 (OUT OF 55)**

Total current number of members: **55 FARMS, 706 PLOTS**

Living lab 2: Continental agricultural soil

Problem:

Intensive agriculture depletes SOM and increases the risk of soil erosion and loss of soil biodiversity

Living Lab #2:

7-year cantonal project on “climate protection through soil organic matter build-up”

- Agricultural school and advisory service:
 - Lead Local bank = Compensation project
 - FiBL = Scientific monitoring
- 55 farms with 706 plots on 1200 Ha participating
- Farm-specific SOM build-up plan (20 agreed measures)
- Standardised sampling and analysis campaign on 706 plots (Year 0, 3 and 6)
- Monitoring of all field and farm actions
- Intense monitoring of 10 representative farms (50 plots; including climate footprint using Cool Farm Tool)
- Result-based payment scheme
- Currently sampling campaign

LIVING LAB #2: Soil health threats

- Loss of soil biodiversity below and above ground
- Intensive agricultural practices
- Depletion of soil organic matter
- Risk of erosion
- Soil and water pollution
- Landscape simplification and cleared hedge rows

Living lab 2: Experimental farm DOK trial #1

- Farming system comparison trial
- Therwil, canton BL, initiated in 1978
- Soil type: Haplic Luvisol
- Soil texture: 3% sand, 75% silt, 22% clay
- 5th year within each 7-year crop rotation period
- Four farming systems × four replicates = 16 samples sampled

Living lab 2: Experimental site #2 (Arable farm)

- Biodynamic farming system; very innovative → many different crops, minimal tillage
- Transfer mulch for potatoes
- Cover crops with up to 10 different components
- Cereals bean mixtures, sesam, oat-vetch mixed cropping
- Five plots (Direct seeding/No-till + various crops) × three replicates = 15 samples

Living lab 2: Experimental site #3 (Mixed farm)

- Intense conventional farming system with reduced and conventional tillage
- Mixed fertilization with slurry and mineral fertilizer
- Three plots (one intense fodder production on grassland and autumn pasture, two arable plots with barley and wheat) × three replicates = Nine samples

Living lab 2: Experimental site #4 (Orchard)

- Fruit tree producer and fruit producer
- Change from conventional cereal field to pear orchard
- Compost application + green manure
- Tree planting in spring
- 1 plot with three sampling locations under trees and three in driveway = Six samples

LIVING LAB #2: Possible solutions to enhance soil health and promote economic activity

- Organic matter built up → via an agreed SOM built up plan and constant monitoring
- Organic amendments
- Reduced tillage
- Reduction of external inputs
- Systematic understanding of ecosystem functioning and services
- Result-based payment for SOM built up
- Remote sensing for regional and temporal **trend analyses**

Annex 2 – Complete list of ecosystem services and soil health indicators associated to measure them

This Annex 1 provides the complete list of soil ecosystem services and the indicators selected to measure them to be selected under participatory approach

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit
Provisioning			
Provision of food (<i>Cultivated crops that can be harvested for direct use and used as raw material for the production of food</i>)	Crop yield	Weight of any economic product per unit of land area harvested	kg/ha
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and Plant Senescing Reflectance Index (PSRI)	Satellite-based vegetation index used to analyse the health, cover and life cycles of vegetation and leaf senescence	Dimensionless
Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials (<i>Biomass or inorganic materials for direct use and/or processed as fibre, energy or for construction</i>)	Plant biomass	Dry weight of shoot and root	kg/ha
	Vegetation cover	Percentage of soil which is covered by green vegetation	%
	Forest cover	Percentage of forest that covers a particular area of land	%
	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Plant Phenology Index (PPI), Dry matter Productivity (DMP) and Leaf area index (LAI)	Satellite-based vegetation index used to analyse the health, cover and life cycles of vegetation	Dimensionless
Provision of water (<i>Surface water retained by soil</i>)	Water content at field capacity	This refers to the water content when the soil becomes dry and plants can no longer take up water and the one left behind after the water contained in the macropores is drained by gravity	cm ³ /cm ³

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit
Regulating			
Climate regulation (<i>Regulation of chemical composition of atmosphere (global regulation) and the air temperature and humidity (micro and regional regulation)</i>)	Total soil organic carbon, C stock and C/N ratio	Potential soil fertility, good soil structure and C sequestration and storage	g/kg, ton/ha
	Particulate organic carbon	Easily degradable plant material, microbial biomass and labile organic materials	g/kg
	Inorganic carbon	Carbonate minerals sequestering CO ₂ in soil	g/kg
	Soil CO ₂ , N ₂ O and CH ₄ emissions	Greenhouse gases involved in climate change	mg/m ² /h
	Field soil moisture	Soil moisture provides a buffer for vegetation during dry periods	cm ³ /cm ³
	Air temperature (mean, lowest, highest)	Measurement of the warmth in the air, affecting plant growth and biochemical processes	°C
	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)	Satellite-based indicators to measure the temperature of the land surface	Dimensionless
	Total ecosystem organic carbon content (TEC)	Sum of the total organic carbon stored in living plant biomass, dead biomass and soil	t/ha
Water/air purification and soil contaminant reduction (<i>Bioremediation and filtration / sequestration / storage / accumulation of water, wastes or toxic substances</i>)	Total and bioavailable heavy metals and metalloids	Soil pollution	mg/kg
	Nitrates	Pollution of surface or groundwater by nitrates	mg/kg
	Pesticides	Pollution by anthropogenic organic substances used to control pests/diseases	ng/g
	Exchangeable Na, electrical conductivity and pH	Salinization, sodification or acidification	mg/kg, dS/m
Nutrient cycling (<i>Originating, storing, transforming, recycling and transferring nutrients from soils into plants</i>)	Total and mineral nitrogen	Essential element for plant nutrition	g/kg, mg/kg
	Available P, K, Ca, Mg and S	Essential macronutrients for plant growth	mg/kg
	Available Fe, Mn, Cu, Zn, B and Mo	Essential micronutrients for plant growth	mg/kg
	Soil pH	Acidity or basicity of a soil, controlling nutrient availability	Dimensionless
	Cation exchange capacity, base saturation, Al concentration and bases/Al ratio	Indices of soil fertility, as the capacity of soil to retain cationic nutrients and growth-limiting factor	cmol/kg and %

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit
Flood regulation and water storage (<i>Regulation of water flow that mitigates or prevents potential damage to economic assets and human lives</i>)	Soil aggregate stability and mean weight diameter	Ability of soil particles that bind together and resist breaking apart	% and mm
	Bulk density and soil porosity	Soil mass per volume that occupies in the field, including pores. Indicator of structure	g/cm ³ and cm ³ /cm ³
	Particle size and coarse fragments	Number of particle size classes in a bulk material	%
	Soil sealing	Permanent covering of soil by impermeable artificial material such as asphalt or concrete	%
	Drought Stress Index, Moisture Stress Index, Sentinel-2 Water Index	Satellite-based vegetation index to measure water content in vegetation and assess the effect of water stress on plants	Dimensionless
Erosion control (<i>Control of erosion rates, including buffering and attenuation of mass movement</i>)	Vegetation cover	Percentage of soil which is covered by green vegetation	%
	Mapping visible soil erosion features	Remote sensing techniques to map soil loss	km
	Bare soil index	Fallow land between two crops or after the land clearance process	Dimensionless

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit
Supporting			
Biodiversity (variety of organisms living in the soil)	Total microbial biomass	Abundance of total microorganisms (bacteria, fungi and protists)	µg/kg or µmol/kg
	Bacterial and fungal diversity, richness and abundance	Indicators of the bacterial and fungal communities	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Protists diversity, richness and abundance	Indicators of the protists community	Dimensionless, species number and number/g
	Richness of Microarthropods richness, abundance and biomass and soil biological quality based on arthropods (QBSar index)	Indicators of the arthropods community	Species number, number/m ² , g/m ² and dimensionless (1-20)
	Spider richness and abundance	Indicators of the community of spiders in the soil	species number and number/day
	Coprophagous fauna richness, abundance and activity	Indicators of the community of coprophagous in the soil	species number, number/day and % of mass loss
Habitat for organisms (<i>Landscape heterogeneity for maintaining nursery populations and habitats, including gene pool protection</i>)	Presence of natural green elements	Presence of native vegetation in croplands	%
	Type of forest species	Different types of trees	number
	Rotation length and sequence	Number of years in which one crop is repeated and different species grown in a 5-year period	yr and number
	Intercropping species	Number of species grown at the same time and land	number
	Plant richness, biodiversity and density	Number of total plant species, diversity and number per surface (for forests and urban landscapes)	Number, dimensionless and plants/m ²
	Soil sealing	Permanent covering of soil by impermeable artificial material such as asphalt or concrete	%

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit	
Cultural	Cultural heritage (<i>Characteristics or features (tangible) of soil systems that have a bequest value to the conservation of physical artefacts of human cultural heritage (such as structures, objects and organisms)</i>)	Presence of cultural elements	Presence of physical/tangible elements (structures, objects) with a significant and social importance for cultural heritage (e.g., terraces, dry stone walls, watermills)	Yes/No (binary)
		Presence of ancestral vestiges	Presence of ancestral vestiges (structures, objects, paleosols, organisms) with an historical and remarkable importance for the site	Yes/No (binary)
	Cultural identity (<i>Characteristics or features (non-tangible) of soil systems that have symbolic meaning and contribute to the promotion of spiritual sense of belonging, traditional knowledge, and associated customs in social systems where they are embedded</i>)	Presence of traditional elements	Presence of traditional elements linked to the ecosystem (e.g., traditional dishes, festivities)	Yes/No (binary)
		Presence of origin certification labelling	Presence of labels identifying the geographic indication of its origin, which is directly related to the assessed ecosystem (e.g., PDO, PGI)	Yes/No (binary)
	Recreation (<i>Characteristics of soil systems that enable its physical use by activities promoting health, recuperation or enjoyment through active or immersive interactions</i>)	Chance of enjoying recreation activities	Theoretical recreation supply based on Euclidean distance to protected areas, water bodies and sites of touristic relevance	0–1 Index (continuous)
Recreation Index		Presence of infrastructure for recreation and accessibility to places	1-17 Index (discrete)	
Visitors and accommodations		Number of visitors to a site and number of tourist accommodations in the area	Number/ha	
Aesthetics (<i>Characteristics of soil systems that enable aesthetic experiences or enjoyment through passive or observational interactions</i>)	Aesthetic landscape Index	Based on naturalness of the landscape, its topography, the diversity of ecosystems), the presence of relevant landscapes, and the influence of negative elements	1-11 Index (discrete)	
	Photo elicitation intensity index	Visual, sensitive and intellectual interaction with the environment, by photos which people take and upload on public virtual spaces.	Number of photos/ha (continuous)	

Soil Ecosystem Services	Indicators	Indicator definition	Unit
Information for cognitive development (<i>Contribution of soil systems to the acquisition of knowledge</i>)	Employment generation	Annual work units (AWU) related to soil management	AWU/ha/year (continuous)
	Knowledge generation	Number of research projects and scientific papers related to the ecosystem	Number (continuous)